

EFFICACY OF PSYCHODYNAMIC PSYCHOTHERAPY IN YOUNG ADULTS:

A REVIEW OF META-ANALYTIC EVIDENCE

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically reviews the study by Trotta et al. (2024), which systematically evaluated the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young adults. Psychodynamic therapy, grounded in psychoanalytic theory, emphasizes unconscious processes, early life experiences, and interpersonal relationships in shaping psychological functioning. The review highlights the therapeutic effectiveness of psychodynamic approaches in reducing symptoms of anxiety, depression, and interpersonal difficulties while promoting long-term psychological growth and emotional resilience. The meta-analysis synthesized evidence from 14 clinical trials, demonstrating significant improvements in clinical outcomes and psychosocial functioning. Despite these findings, limitations such as sample heterogeneity, small study sizes, and methodological inconsistencies warrant further research. This paper underscores the relevance of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young adults and its integration into modern clinical practice while identifying areas for future investigation.

1. Introduction and Historical background of Psychoanalysis

Psychoanalysis has evolved significantly overtime, since its origins with Sigmund Freud, the pioneer and father of the school of thought in the late 19th century (1890). *Psychoanalysis* significantly influenced psychology with the introduction of the concepts of the unconscious mind with a specific emphasis on the impact of early childhood experiences on personality and behavioural development, (Kenny, 2017). Freud's work laid the groundwork for understanding mental health and its background, the conflicts of the mind, identity, relationship dynamics and defenses mechanisms. Freud made a significant contribution to psychotherapeutic approaches with his *psychodynamic treatment modality* which includes techniques such as dream analysis, and free association, (Kenny, 2017, Messer, 2015). Overtime the approach had evolved and expanded and yet has retained the focus on unconscious drives and early childhood experiences to incorporating diverse fields on interpersonal, cultural, neuropsychology and neurobiological perspectives.

This evolution was shaped in the early 20th century by scholars and neo-Freudians such Carl Jung, originally a disciple of Freud who contributed significantly to the evolution of psychoanalysis by developing the *analytical psychology*, which emphasized the *collective unconscious* and *archetypes*, (Vibhute & Kumar, 2024). Jung expanded on Freud's theories by incorporating broader cultural and spiritual aspects of the individual psyche, influencing the comprehension of human behavior beyond Freud's *individual unconscious drives*. Jung's work on *individuation* and the integration of opposites remains a key aspect of psychotherapy in today's post-modernist and meta modernistic era of the psychodynamic thought, (Tarzian & Fakoya, et al, 2023; Vibhute et al, 2024).

In the period of the 20th century, Melanie Klein and John Bowlby further expanded Freud's ideologies. Klein's *object relations* theory underscored the concept of early relationships and internalized representations of others, which significantly influenced later psychodynamic methodologies, (Kenny, 2016). On the other hand, Bowlby introduced the concept of *attachment theories*, explaining how early bonds with the primary caregivers can impact emotional development and relationship patterns throughout one's life. This approach is closely related to Freud's concept of *internal working models*, *fixation*, and the unfolding of *childhood traumas and psychosexual developmental milestones*, (Fulmer, 2018). This concept was later refined by Mary Ainsworth into *attachment styles* (secure, anxious, avoidant) which closely related to Freud's *defence mechanism, drives and inner conflict's philosophy*.

The mid-20th century period saw the emergence of other contributors to the evolution of psychoanalysis and psychodynamic, that id Erick Erickson *psycho-social development* that expanded from Freud's psychosexual stages to incorporate the social

aspects and expand on identity and developmental milestones, (Fulmer, 2018). Heinz Kohut's *self-psychology* which shifted the focus to empathy and self-cohesion expanded from Freud's ideologies of the self and the *narcissistic personality*. Stephen Mitchell's *relational psychoanalysis* highlighted the mutual influence between therapist and patient, thus building on Freud's intercepts of *transference and relational philosophy*, (Kenny, 2016; Kenny, 2017; Fulmer 2018). Today the psychoanalytic movement remains relevant and continuously growing with the modernistic evolution in therapy.

2. Critical Psychodynamic Therapy Historical Background

The key foundational techniques that form the psychodynamic therapy are free association, transference and counter transference analysis, interpretation, resistance analysis, catharsis and the therapist client relationship, (Fulmer, 2018). Sigmund Freud introduced the foundational techniques of *psychodynamic therapeutic modality* in the late to early 1900, while working with his patients who had hysteria another psychological symptom that did not have a clear cause. His early work with patients such as Anna O and Dora, led to the exploration of unconscious drives and repressed memories as well as inner conflicts as central to psychotherapy and mental health, (Freud, 1905, Gonzalez, 2016, Mustafa, 2018). Freud's clinical observation with cases formed the basis of the development of all his therapeutic techniques in psychodynamic, (Freud, 1905).

Freud placed a significant focus on the *free association technique* that encouraged patients to verbalise thoughts without filtering them. He also published *dream analysis* in his publication on *The Interpretation of dreams* and *the Psychopathology of everyday life*, published in German in 1900 and 1901, (Holmes, 2017). Freud explored the concept of free association and analysed what was termed the "Freudian slips" (slips of the tongue), interpreting them as windows into the unconscious. This publication introduced Freud's ideologies on how dreams reflect unconscious desires, fears, and conflicts, marking a foundational moment for psychoanalysis and the technique of dream analysis, (Holmes, 2017, Messer, 2013). In 1905 Freud published the *Fragments of an Analysis of a Case of Hysteria (Dora)*. In this case study, Freud applied and documented *transference and countertransference* concepts in therapy for the first time, (patients' projections of feelings onto the therapist), (Mustafa, 2018). A publication in 1910 on the *Five Lectures on Psychoanalysis* presented by Freud during his lectures at Clark University presented the overview of psychodynamic techniques, including *resistance and interpretation*, (Freud, 1909, Freud, 1955, Freud, 1977).

In 1914, Freud published his work on *Remembering, Repeating, and Working-Through*. Freud explored *resistance analysis* and the importance of *catharsis*, detailing how bringing repressed emotions into consciousness allows for psychological healing,

(Freud, 1977, Freud, 1914, Freud, 1950). *The Introductory Lectures on Psychoanalysis* from 1916 to 1917, a collection of Freud's lectures provides in-depth explanations of free association, *interpretation*, transference, and other core psychoanalytic techniques, (Freud, 1909).

Each of these literatures not only describes Freud's techniques but also illustrates their application through case studies, allowing for a deeper comprehension of the theory and practice of psychodynamic therapy. Freud's original psychodynamic approach was an elongated modalities that took months and even years working with a patient. The emergence of analytic psychology and ego psychology continued to improve and evolve psychodynamic therapy. In the 1960s to 1980s, a *brief short term psychodynamic therapy* (STDP), was developed by scholars Strupp and Sifneos, in response to the growing need for a shorter and practical modality, (Eppel, 2018, Center for Substance Abuse Treatment, 1999, Demos, 1993, Abbass et al., 2014). the STDP has fewer sessions that also address immediate symptoms making it a time limited approach while retaining traditional psychodynamic principles. This approach remains popular today's psychotherapeutic practice. Psychodynamic continued to evolve with the development of Mitchell and Sullivan's *Interpersonal therapy* (IPT), founded in the principles of relational and interpersonal psychology which emerged from psychoanalysis. This psychodynamic modality focuses on interpersonal relationships and the therapist and client relationship itself, therefore making therapy more collaborative and adaptive to the client's experiences, (Markowitz, 2004, Lipsitz & Markowitz, 2013).

Present day psychodynamic therapy has a major collaborative approach with findings form neuroscience and attachment theories, (Bowlby). This integrates traditional techniques with evidence-based approaches in the application of attachment modalities such as *Mentalisation based therapy* (MBT) and *Transference Focused therapy* (TFP), to address specific conditions like borderline personality disorder making psychodynamic a structured evidence-based therapy in the modern-day era, (Hersh, et al, 2016). Today, psychodynamic therapy remains an influential treatment for various mental health conditions, emphasizing insight, emotional awareness, and the therapeutic relationship. Today, psychodynamic therapy integrates diverse perspectives, also drawing from neurobiology to understand the mind-brain connection, making it a more holistic and relational approach to mental health and wellness.

This paper will review the work of Trotta et al. (2024), who conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young adults. Their study synthesized evidence from multiple trials, revealing that psychodynamic therapy is effective in addressing a range of psychological issues in young adults, including anxiety, depression, and interpersonal

difficulties. The authors highlight the therapeutic benefits of psychodynamic approaches, particularly in fostering long-term psychological growth and emotional resilience.

3. Overview of Trotta et al. (2024)' Study

The efficacy of psychodynamic therapy, particularly for young adults, has received little attention when compared to other therapeutic modalities such as cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), (Trotta et al, 2024, Pilecki, et al, 2015). Young adulthood is a significant developmental period marked by substantial psychological and emotional obstacles such as identity formation, relationship dynamics, and the transition to independence., (Pilecki, et al, 2015). As mental health problems among young adults worsen, there is an urgent need for effective treatment strategies suited to this group.

A systematic review and meta-analysis study conducted by Trotta et al. (2024) aimed to fill this gap by evaluating the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy specifically for young adults aged between 18 and 27 years. This demographic is often characterized by unique psychological challenges, making it essential to explore tailored therapeutic interventions. The authors conducted a systematic assessment of the literature using numerous electronic databases, including Ovid, Embase, PubMed, PsychINFO, and Cochrane, to identify relevant papers published before July 2023. Through synthesizing these existing studies, the researchers aimed to provide a comprehensive understanding of how psychodynamic therapy can address the unique mental health needs of this population. This study not only adds to the empirical evidence for psychodynamic approaches, but it also emphasizes the significance of establishing specific interventions that address the developmental issues that young adults encounter in their lives. As clinical psychology changes, practitioners aiming to provide the best effective psychotherapeutic care to their clients must grasp the efficacy of various therapeutic modalities for effective mental health outcomes. This paper will critically review the findings of Trotta et al. (2024), focusing on the research's strengths and limitations while also exploring the larger implications for clinical practice and future research in the field.

The research strategy employed by Trotta et al. (2024), focused on studies that examined psychodynamic or psychoanalytic therapies, with the inclusion criteria specifically targeting participants that are young adults, who were receiving treatment for mental health problems. The meta-analysis employed randomized controlled trials (RCTs) as well as quasi-experimental studies, and the application of naturalistic evaluations that reported quantitative outcomes for the psychodynamic therapeutic intervention studies. The researcher followed the principles of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) which provided them

with guidelines to ensure a rigorous and transparent methodological review, (Trotta et al. 2024).

4. Key Findings

In terms of efficacy of psychodynamic therapy, the meta-analysis comprised 14 clinical trials, that showed that psychodynamic psychotherapy is a *viable treatment (effective treatment)* choice for young people. The data demonstrated considerable improvements in clinical symptoms and general functioning, with a notable effect size (Hedges' g of -1.24) therefore implying that psychodynamic therapy is significantly successful treatment modality for positive mental health outcomes of young adults. This finding aligns with existing literature in several key areas. In terms of the efficacy and viability of psychodynamic therapy, Trotta et al. report improvements in mental health and psychosocial functioning for young adults, consistent with studies by Leichsenring and Leibing (2003) and Steinert et al. (2017), who found similar effectiveness for various psychological disorders. Trotta et al.'s emphasis on transformation mechanisms, such as transference and emotional processing, is consistent with Shedler (2010) and Fonagy et al. (2014), who emphasize the therapeutic relationship and insight.

Psychodynamic therapy's level of *sustained effect* demonstrated a positive and maintained long term mental health outcomes on follow up with an effect size of $g = -0.75$ ($p < 0.001$). This indicated that psychodynamic therapy benefits continued beyond the immediate treatment period for young adults. This finding promotes symptom reduction, deeper psychological changes and enhance overall life satisfaction for young adults affected by a mental illness, (Trotta et al. 2024). The 14 trials addressed a *diverse clinical application*. It included studies that investigated the efficacy of psychodynamic therapy on emotional disorders that included depression and anxiety, as well as specific populations such as individuals with eating disorders and personality disorders. The evidence of diversity in the clinical trials therefore shows the versatility of psychodynamic therapy in addressing a range of psychological issues among young adults. Trotta et al. (2024), also stated *cultural considerations*, which is crucial, as Tummala-Narra, (2013) suggests adapting psychodynamic therapy for diverse cultural backgrounds. Trotta et al.'s call for more research on long-term outcomes is supported by Abbass et al. (2013), who noted the need for further investigation into the sustainability of benefits.

A randomized trial study conducted by Rahmani et al. (2020) to assess the efficacy of intensive short-term psychodynamic psychotherapy for social anxiety disorder, focusing on feelings versus defenses work found the therapeutic intervention to be effective in mental health outcomes and long-term maintenance. According to Riva Crugnola et al. (2020), a psychodynamic-based university

counselling intervention showed effectiveness in supporting students. Trotta et al. (2024) found that psychodynamic when compared to other studies presented the *same efficacy level as other therapeutic modalities* like cognitive behavioural therapy in collaboration with pharmacotherapy, this aligns with Cuijpers et al. (2016), who found both therapies effective for different issues. These findings present that psychodynamic can be as effective as other therapies in this population of young adults. While the study focused on the efficacy on the treatment on symptom reduction, significant improvements were noted for broader psychosocial functioning which included personality and social functioning, (Kenny, 2016). This finding suggests that psychodynamic therapy may *offer benefits beyond mere symptomatic relief*. The study also found that psychodynamic psychotherapy may be an effective strategy for *treating young people' complex mental health issues*, underlining the need for additional study to investigate the long-term efficacy and particular processes of change associated with this therapeutic approach, (Trotta et al. 2024).

The findings of the study supported the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young adults, advocating for its inclusion in treatment options for this demographic group, while also calling for further research to refine and expand upon these findings.

5. Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework of Trotta et al. (2024) in their article on the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young adults is grounded in psychoanalytic theory, which emphasizes the role of unconscious processes, early life experiences, and interpersonal relationships in shaping psychological functioning, (Freud, 1905, Summers et al, 2024). Key concepts in this framework include the *unconscious mind*, where unconscious thoughts influence behavior, and psychodynamic therapy aims to bring these processes to awareness, (Summers et al, 2024). The *therapeutic relationship* plays a critical role, with *transference* and *countertransference* helping uncover deep-seated emotional patterns. *Defence mechanisms*, such as repression and denial, are also addressed to promote healthier coping strategies. The theory underscores the importance of *developmental perspectives*, viewing young adulthood as a critical period for identity formation and resolving past conflicts, (Riva et al, 2020, Summers, 2024). Additionally, psychodynamic therapy highlights the role of *interpersonal relationships* in emotional well-being. Through increased self-awareness, emotional processing, and insight into relational patterns, the therapy fosters symptom reduction and improved functioning, demonstrating its effectiveness for young adults' psychological needs, (Freud, 1977, Riva et al, 2020).

6. Critical Analysis of Psychodynamic Therapy and Methodology

The work by Trotta et al. (2024) offers a persuasive case for the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young adults, stressing its distinctive contributions to mental health treatment. However, some crucial considerations should be considered. Trotta et al. (2024) offer useful insights into the efficacy evidence for psychodynamic therapy in young adults. While the study confirms its usefulness, the authors point out that many previous studies have focused on children and adults, with little research explicitly addressing young adults. Research studies especially quantitative studies that are embedded in empirical evidence or evidence based approached need to produce findings that are reliable, valid and can be generalised across populations, (Smith, 2018). This finding raises concerns on the findings are *generalizable*, highlighting the need for more research on this demographic. The study also underlines the significance of knowing psychodynamic therapy's transformation mechanisms, which include transference, defensive mechanisms, and emotional processing, (Palecki et al, 2015). However, distinguishing components that contribute to therapeutic results remains difficult, implying that future research should focus on clarifying these mechanisms to improve knowledge of how psychodynamic therapy promotes change, (Palecki et al, 2015).

Trotta et al., (2024) acknowledge the limitations of their *small sample sizes* and potential publication bias, a concern shared by Smith, (2017), who emphasized the need for more rigorous studies for generalisability. While their findings support the efficacy of psychodynamic therapy for young adults, they also highlight the need for additional research into comparative effectiveness, cultural adaptations, and long-term outcomes. In terms of *comparative effectiveness*, while the review compares psychodynamic therapy to other treatments, it does not deeply explore how psychodynamic therapy compares to other modalities like cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT). A more in-depth exploration would be beneficial for clinicians in selecting appropriate treatments for young adults. The study being a meta-analysis does not accommodate for a deeper exploration of concepts like qualitative studies which apply content analysis and ethnographical studies that allow the researcher to speak to the participants and explore meaning and the dynamics of the various treatment modalities in the search for efficacy confirmation, (Tenny et al, 2022). The study by Trotta et al, (2024) also discusses the importance of cultural and contextual concerns, noting that psychodynamic therapy's foundations in Western thought may not adequately account for young adults' different backgrounds. Future research should investigate how psychodynamic therapy ideas might be altered to better assist people from different cultural backgrounds.

Trotta et al.'s (2024) inclusion criteria were well-defined, focused on young adults getting psychodynamic treatment for mental health difficulties; nonetheless,

the lack of a sample size cut-off may contribute to inconsistency in study quality, making it difficult to make solid findings. While the study mentions quality assessment, it does not provide a detailed account of the process, which is crucial for understanding the reliability of the findings. Trotta et al. (2024) acknowledged many limitations in their review, such as the need for higher-quality studies and the possibility of publication bias. This transparency lends credibility to their work while also emphasizing the continuous need for additional study to better understand the efficacy of psychodynamic therapy for young adults.

The *study's strengths* include its comprehensive strategy, which employs a systematic review and meta-analysis in quantitative research that increase the dependability of the conclusions, (Smith, 2017). Furthermore, the emphasis on young adults, a demographic that is frequently disregarded in psychotherapy research, yields useful information for targeted therapies, (Vibhute et al, 2024) The study's different data sources contribute to a better understanding of the effectiveness of psychodynamic treatment in the actual world. However, the study also has *several weaknesses*. One significant limitation is the limited number of studies included in the review, which restricts the generalizability of the findings. The authors themselves note the need for more high-quality randomized controlled trials (RCTs) to strengthen the evidence base. Another drawback is the variability of studies, which varies in treatment duration, intervention style, and participant demographics. This variability hampers cross-study comparisons and may alter the consistency of the findings. Finally, the studies included in the study have the potential for bias, mainly due to researcher affiliation and the lack of blinding in outcome assessments. This could affect the therapies claimed effectiveness.

7. Implications for the Field of Clinical Psychology

Trotta et al.'s (2024) findings have significant implications for clinical psychology. To begin, the validation of psychodynamic therapy is an important takeaway, since research showing its efficacy in young people helps legitimize this therapeutic technique within the larger field of psychotherapy. This may prompt practitioners to explore psychodynamic therapy as a potential treatment option for people in this age bracket. Second, the study emphasizes the significance of providing mental health treatments that are specifically adapted to the unique psychological issues that young adults experience.

Furthermore, the study serves as a motivator for future research, emphasizing the importance of more rigorous investigations, such as randomized controlled trials (RCTs) with greater sample sizes and different populations. This could lead to a better understanding of how psychodynamic treatment can be tailored to different

individuals and situations. Finally, the data show that clinicians may benefit from incorporating insights into their practice. Aside from symptom relief, psychodynamic therapy offers the ability to improve emotional resilience and interpersonal functioning, providing a more comprehensive approach to treatment. While the study provides promising evidence for the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy for young people, it also emphasizes the need for additional research to address the study's weaknesses and increase understanding of its practical applications.

8. Conclusion

Trotta et al. (2024) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis, revealing compelling evidence for the efficacy of psychodynamic psychotherapy in treating young adults with psychological issues. The findings suggest that psychodynamic therapies can lead to significant improvements in clinical symptoms and general functioning, establishing them as a viable therapy choice alongside other well-established psychotherapeutic approach. Despite these positive results, the review points up numerous significant limitations. The substantial level of heterogeneity among the included research calls into question the findings' generalizability. Furthermore, much research concentrated on short-term interventions, although psychodynamic therapy is well-known for its long-term and open-ended approach. This disparity highlights the need for further high-quality randomized controlled trials (RCTs) that more accurately reflect the typical duration and structure of psychodynamic treatment in clinical settings. The review also mentions potential biases in psychotherapy research, such as researcher affiliation and a lack of blinding among outcome assessors, emphasizing the significance of methodological rigor in future studies. This review has broader implications for mental health practice and policy than just academic research. Given that over 75% of mental health problems appear in young adulthood, our findings advocate the inclusion of psychodynamic psychotherapy in treatment choices for this susceptible population. By addressing young adults' individual developmental requirements, mental health professionals can better adapt therapies to help them move into adulthood.

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